

European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure
PLUS

Piloting of eLTER specific downstream services contributing to eLTER Standard Observation Variables

Deliverable D4.4

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Prepared under contract from the European Commission

Grant agreement No. 871128

EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation action

Project acronym: **eLTER PLUS**
 Project full title: **European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure PLUS**
 Start of the project: Feb 2020
 Duration: 60 months
 Project coordinator: Professor Jaana Bäck
 University of Helsinki, Finland
<https://www.lter-europe.net/projects/elter-plus>

Deliverable title: Piloting of eLTER specific downstream services contributing to eLTER Standard Observation Variables

Deliverable n°: D4.4

Nature of the deliverable: Report

Dissemination level: Public

Citation: Díaz-Delgado, R., García-Díaz, D., Marangi, C., Silver, M., Oggioni, A., Tagliolato, P., Karnieli, A., Peterseil, J., Vicario, S., Anttila, S., Böttcher, K., Bolton, W., Wohner, C., & Minić, V. (2024). *Piloting of eLTER specific downstream services contributing to eLTER Standard Observation Variables*. Deliverable D4.4 EU Horizon 2020 eLTER PLUS Project, Grant agreement No. 871128.

Deliverable status:

Version	Status	Date	Author(s)
1.0	Draft	3 November 2023	Ricardo Díaz-Delgado & Diego García (CSIC)
1.1	Draft for internal review	18 November 2023	Ricardo Díaz-Delgado & Diego García (CSIC)
2.0	Reviewed draft	10 March 2024	R. Díaz-Delgado, Ulf Mallast, Rita Bastos, Jan Dick, Jaana Bäck, Marie-Noelle Pons
2.1	Draft for second review	7 June 2024	R. Díaz-Delgado, Jaana Bäck, Carmela Marangi
2.2	Final version	23 July 2024	Ricardo Díaz-Delgado

The content of this deliverable does not necessarily reflect the official opinions of the European Commission or other institutions of the European Union.

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Glossary

API	Application Programming Interface
dataLab	eLTER Data Laboratory
DEIMS-SDR	Dynamic Ecological Information System - Site and Dataset Registry, being the central site catalog for eLTER
DEIMS.iD	DEIMS-SDR (persistent site) identifier
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research
EnvThes	Environmental thesaurus
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSD	End of the season Day of the year
EOSV	End of the season Index value
ESA	European Space Agency
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
GEE	Google Earth Engine
GTIFF	Geotiff raster format
HR-VPP	High Resolution Vegetation Phenology Product
IC	eLTER Information Clusters
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IS	eLTER Information System
MOSD	Maximum of the season Day of the year
MOSV	Maximum of the season Index value
NetCDF	Netcdf raster format
PID	(Unique) Persistent Identifier
RC	Research challenges
RI	Research Infrastructure
SES	Research challenge Socio-ecological systems
SO	eLTER Standard Observations
SOS	Sensor Observation Service defined by the Open Geospatial Consortium
SOSD	Start of the season Day of the year
SOSV	Start of the season Index value
SWE	OGC Sensor Web Enablement
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
UML	Unified Modeling Language
LST	Land Surface Temperature
NDWI	Normalized Difference Water Index
MNDWI	Modified Normalized Difference Water Index
AWEI	Automated Water Extraction Index

Preface

The usage of data from all available sources is needed to broaden the thematic, spatial and temporal scope and enable gap filling of in-situ data measured directly at eLTER facilities (eLTER Sites and eLTSER Platforms). WP4 aims to define strategies and workflows by eliciting prior knowledge for integration of data from multiple sources, including eLTER legacy data and external information sources (e.g. gridded data, other in-situ data, Earth Observation products and official statistics). WP4 focuses on priority variables and information in the catalog of eLTER Standard Observations (SO) defined under WP3 (D3.2) and supports the WP8 and WP9 Case Studies. WP4 has triggered the service development carried out by WP11, both in terms of establishing the structures for incorporating information into eLTER Digital Visualization portal (DiV) (WP11.2) and considering them in datasets discovery and visualization (WP11.3). Linkages also exist with WP2 concerning data needs from network users and collaboration with potential providers of information, including co-location. WP4 particularly focuses on Earth Observation available data and products such as the ones provided by Copernicus.

Task 4.4 has been developed linked to the Tasks 3.2 and 4.3. It has focused on priority variables defined under WP3 for rapid harvesting and user uptake. The task has identified the potential RS data sources matching those SO to be used for the piloting of specific data validation. Cross-domain variables such as Vegetation Phenology (SOBIO_016), Water Level (SOHYD_005) and Soil Temperature (SOHYD_168) have been prioritized in order to provide comparative trends from terrestrial and freshwater eLTER Sites.

The main purpose of Task 4.4 was to assess the feasibility of retrieving those variables of high priority for eLTER SO from Earth Observation services based on previous experiences. The pilot study has revealed the needs and requirements and a coarse cost assessment as input to the eLTER ESFRI process. The selected pilot variables were assessed on their accuracy, feasibility and costs as a potential eLTER downstream service to be provided by the eLTER RI.

Several sites for the piloting were selected according to the provision of in-situ datasets. eLTSER Platforms have been focal areas. The Task provides a list of recommended variables to be validated by upscaling with in-situ data and has tested the accuracy of such SO for several eLTER facilities. Validation of these products is an essential step to eLTER RI becoming a formal in-situ validation network for [Copernicus in-situ Component](#). The resulting validated products will be released through the eLTER DiV (WP11) as downstream services for access by end users. Currently [DataLabs](#) is temporarily providing such services. Site and Platform Coordinators' views on the products were assessed during specific presentations at the 3rd Site and Platform Forum (SPF03, May 2022). Specific material for end user training (WP5) was produced after the training workshop on eLTER tools (February 2023, Lyon, France).

Finally, Task 4.4 has benefitted from the complementary research project [SUMHAL](#), "Sustainability for Mediterranean Hotspots in Andalusia integrating LifeWatch ERIC" (SUMHAL, LIFEWATCH-2019-09-CSIC-4, POPE 2014-2020) funded by the European Regional Development Funds. The main goal of its WP6 was to implement a joint task force between eLTER Research Infrastructure and LifeWatch-ERIC as a co-location exercise. Figure 1 shows the overall workflow used for the pilot study of Task 4.4.

Figure 1. Workflow of the Task 4.4 pilot exercise starting by selection of eLTER Standard Observations (SO). DataLabs is temporarily used for provision of tools and eLTER Data Visualization Portal (DiV) for In-Situ collection and as final repository of produced datasets.

Summary

This task is complementary to eLTER PLUS Tasks 3.2 (eLTER PLUS contributions to strengthening the functional nexus between remote sensing and in-situ observations) and 4.3 (Harvesting and harmonizing of Remote Sensing products) and seeks to assess spatial and temporal accuracy of Earth Observation (EO) products and services in relation to selected eLTER Standard Observations (SO) measured in-situ. The task has been implemented as a pilot study including:

- Review of existing EO products & services (Copernicus, GEOSS, etc.) as potential proxies for SO
- Identification of cross-domain SOs with widespread use across eLTER sites
- Prioritization of SO matching specific EO products and services
- Sites selection for pilot test according to available in-situ data
- Pilot implementation through developed tools in DataLabs and accuracy assessment including upscaling methods

Task 4.4. has proceeded in parallel to Task 3.2. on strengthening the functional nexus between Earth Observation and in-situ data from eLTER sites and platforms which can meet the requirements for calibration and validation (cal/val) of Earth Observation products and services.

Both tasks have addressed the Copernicus in-situ component, led by EEA, defining a list of requirements and a roadmap to facilitate eLTER RI future integration in Copernicus cal/val networks. The task has also contributed to the RCs Biodiversity (Task 8.1 Biodiversity loss) and Socio-Ecology (Task 4.5 LTSE pilot data provisioning – utilizing RI expertise for spatially-explicit socio-ecological data provision to platforms) with the developed tools and the generated EO products.

1 Standard Observations (SO) prioritization and selection

In eLTER PLUS Deliverable 3.2, relevant eLTER SO for in-situ validation of Earth Observation products were identified. For many Earth Observation products, there is not yet a well-defined protocol or

method for the collection of available in-situ observations. The validation activities are in many cases adjusted to the available information. As a pilot exercise and according to the available in-situ datasets from eLTER Sites we selected the following SO representing different eLTER spheres:

- **Land Surface Phenology:** Under eLTER Biosphere the Vegetation Phenology (SOBIO_016) describes the seasonal changes in vegetation greenness and photosynthetic leaf area at the landscape scale, including canopy green-up date (start of season), peak date, senescence date (end of season) and season length, measured in day of year. Plant phenological events can be obtained from eddy covariance measurements, ground-based imaging such as phenocams or continuous spectral measurements; species-specific phenological observations. Currently no validation protocol exists. CEOS LPVS and the Ground-Based Observations for Validation (GBOV) of Copernicus Global Land Products are working on a validation good practice protocol and golden standard LSP validation database. The [Copernicus High Resolution Vegetation Phenology and Productivity](#) product was developed after the start of Task 4.4. Before its release in September 2022 (Tian et al. 2021), Task 4.4 focused on filling the gap of phenology metrics derived from Sentinel-2 images.
- **Water bodies delineation:** For the eLTER Hydrosphere the Water Level (SOHYD_005) is identified as a priority group of SO to be used for validation of Earth Observation products. Therefore, it is crucial as a first step to delineate water bodies and surface water occurrence for eLTER aquatic sites, either permanent or seasonal wetlands. Discriminating water presence will provide the basis raster mask to apply for the retrieval of water physico-chemical parameters, discarding terrestrial or non-inundated areas from any further analysis. Periodical water bodies delineation by using time series of satellite images enables the retrieval of inundation/flooding frequency or hydroperiod, which reveals the effects of extreme climate events such as drought or floods. Hydroperiod trends and anomalies can evidence hydrological changes and watershed management.
- **Land Surface Temperature:** Also, under the eLTER Hydrosphere, Soil Surface Temperature (SOHYD_168) is identified as an essential in-situ SO of interest for Earth Observation products validation. Land Surface Temperature (LST) is a widely available Earth Observation product from different thermal sensors onboard satellites, although most of them have a low spatial resolution (from the 1 km pixel size of MODIS to the 300 m of Sentinel-3) or low revisiting time (such as the 30 m pixel size of the Landsat 8 and 9 satellites). Nonetheless, fiducial measurements of radiometric temperature can easily be retrieved with in-situ thermal sensors, enabling not only the validation of LST but also the calibration.

2 Description of the tools developed

In order to comply with Task 4.4 goals, we have developed the online tool [GeeLTERMap](#), a Python package that enables the visualization, query and download of the different selected Standard Observations (SO): Land Surface Phenology, Water bodies delineation and Land Surface Temperature for any eLTER Site.

During the development of GeeLTERMap, two complementary Python libraries for downloading and processing satellite images on the cloud have been developed and distributed as Python packages through the [Python Software Foundation](#) (PyPi). These two additional libraries are [PyVPP](#) and [NDVI2GIF](#). The 3 libraries integrate DEIMS-SDR API ([deimsPy](#)) to retrieve the spatial boundaries of

eLTER Sites enabling to serve the mosaicked and cropped images of the selected variable for the requested eLTER Site using boundaries provided by [DEIMS-SDR](#). Figure 2 shows a flow chart of the three developed tools.

Figure 2: Flowchart of the three developed tools under Task 4.4.

2.1 PyVPP: A python package to retrieve Earth Observation products for eLTER sites and platforms

[PyVPP](#) is a Python package developed to download EO data from WEkEO stitched and cropped to any user-defined region (Figure 3). [WEkEO](#) is the EU Copernicus DIAS reference portal to provide downstream services for environmental data as well as virtual processing environments and expert user support, from which a registered user can access Earth Observation data and products from ESA Sentinel satellites. Among the many available EO products at WEkEO, PyVPP allows the user to prepare and download the following vegetation datasets from Sentinel 2 images (10 m pixel size and 5 days revisiting time):

- Vegetation Indices
- Vegetation Seasonal Trajectories
- Vegetation Phenology and Productivity Parameters

In addition to the vegetation products, the SLSTR dataset from Sentinel-3 has also been added for retrieving Land Surface Temperature images (1000 m pixel size and daily images) for any eLTER Site. The datasets offered by PyVPP, with their main characteristics, are summarized in Table 1. However, only full scene download (1400 km swath) of LST is possible by means of PyVPP. Native Sentinel 3 files are provided in NetCDF format which limits the processing. For this Sentinel-3 product, clipping to site boundaries is pending for a future update of the tool. Nonetheless, this product serves as an additional complement to PyVPP since the LSTApp tool integrated in GeeLTERMap provides land surface temperature products from Landsat (30 m pixel size and images every 8 days with alternated Landsat 8 and 9 acquisitions) and MODIS images (500 m pixel size and daily images).

The use of PyVpp is very simple. The script can either take a shapefile or just a DEIMS ID as input (remember to add "deimsid:yoursiteid" while selecting this option). The geometry (shp or DEIMS ID) is read by the library as a geodataframe, the extent of which is calculated in order to download all intersecting images for the selected period. Once the images are downloaded, they are grouped by date and product and the site mosaic created by clipping the images to the eLTER site spatial boundaries. Such clipped mosaics with the selected product are downloaded to a new folder in your local directory called *pyhda* where the final products are saved using the following nomenclature: "mosaic_selectedvariable_rec.tif" where *selectedvariable* will be the name of the selected variable.

Figure 3: PyVPP python library main page

Table 1: Specifications of available HR-VPP products from PyVPP.

Dataset Name	Spatial Resolution	Temporal Resolution	Variables	Format
VPP Pheno	10 m	Yearly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SOSD ● SOSV ● MOSD ● MOSV ● EOSD ● EOSV 	GTIFF
VPP Index	10 m	5 days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NDVI ● PPI ● FAPAR ● LAI 	GTIFF
VPP ST	10 m	10 days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PPI 	GTIFF-
SLSTR	1 km	Daily	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● LST 	NetCDF

The only required inputs to run PyVPP are the geometry, the name of the collection, the name of the variables to download, and the desired time period. The package can also be installed locally and run using command prompts as follows:

```
import pyvpp
# Second parameter could be replaced with any shapefile or deimsID
MyWekeo = pyvpp.wekeo_download("VPP_Index",
"deimsid:https://deims.org/bcbc866c-3f4f-47a8-bbbc-0a93df6de7b2",
['2018-01-01', '2018-06-30'], ['LAI', 'FAPAR'])
MyWekeo.run()
```

The package can also be executed in a virtual environment such as [Google colab](#) or the [Datalabs](#). A PyVPP Jupyter notebook (pyvpp.ipynb) is available in the 'Notebooks' section under GeelTERMap repository in the eLTER RI project. A Google colab notebook is also available using the following link: [PyVpp eLTER example.ipynb](#). An important info for users of PyVPP in a virtual environment such as Datalabs, is that the download from Wekeo requests to create a config file named `“.hdarc”`, where WEKEO user and password are stored (previous registration in WEKEO portal is necessary). While running locally PyVPP `.hdarc` file has to be created in the local home folder. But, when Datalab or any other virtual/shared environment is used for PyVPP, it is highly recommended that you use the two detailed command prompts for `hdarc` file creation and deletion. The commands are: `fillHda()` and `delHdaInfo()`. Both functions are included with PyVPP and can be prompted as follows:

```
fillHda("youruser", "yourpassword")
# Do your work and when it's done delete the .hdarc file
delHdaInfo()
```

There is also a straightforward procedure to execute PyVPP in a loop across all sites and select SO for any national network or for all eLTER sites. This procedure can be implemented within DataLabs in order to store and catalog all PyVPP products for eLTER sites, which could afterwards be provided as downstream services using [eLTER Digital Visualization portal \(DiV\)](#) as scheduled under WP11.

As an example, the next code block will get the Vegetation Indexes (PPI, NDVI, FAPAR and LAI) for all the sites included in the eLTER Spain network.

```
import deims
# List all the sites of a national network
elter_spain = deims.getListOfSites("2b70f1fb-f7d9-4615-a1a3-33fc6fa44600")
all_elter_sites = deims.getListOfSites()
# Base name to add to the deimsID to get the correct url
base = "deimsid:https://deims.org/"
# Just change elter_spain for all_elter_sites to get the whole elter
for site in elter_spain:
    # Print site name
    nsite = base + site
    # Start the process
    try:
        a = wekeo_download('VPP_Index', nsite, ['2022-01-01', '2022-12-31'], ['PPI', 'NDVI', 'FAPAR', 'LAI'])
```

```
a.run()
except Exception as e:
    print(e)
    continue
```

In order to enhance the usability of PyVPP (5 stargazers, 1 fork and 1 open issue as Github indicators up to March 2024), a video tutorial has been produced to fully describe the tool's (Figure 4). The video tutorial can be accessed through the following link: <https://youtu.be/LpmaqW1mBXM> which has already been viewed by 33 Youtube users up to March 2024.

Figure 4: Screen capture of the PyVPP video tutorial.

2.2 NDVI2GIF: A python package for RGB composites of phenology

[NDVI2GIF](#) (Figure 5) is a python library designed to create Seasonal Composites of standard EO indices, based on different basic statistics applied to some EO datasets. This tool uses [Google Earth Engine](#) API and [Geemap python package](#) to create seasonal RGB composites based on spectral vegetation indices.

This tool has been updated in the framework of eLTER Plus and SUMHAL projects, as it is the main input to the [PhenoPy](#) python package (see below), which is the library to retrieve the phenology metrics derived from such seasonal composites.

The stats included at this point are:

- Maximum
- Mean
- Median
- Percentile 90
- Percentile 95

The available indices are:

- **NDVI** (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index)
- **EVI** (Enhanced Vegetation Index)
- **SAVI** (Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index)
- **GNDVI** (Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index)
- **AVI** (Advanced Vegetation Index)

- **NBRI** (Normalized Burn Ratio Index)
- **NDSI** (Normalized Difference Snow Index)
- **AEWI** (Automated Water Extraction Index)

Figure 5: Front page of the NDVI2GIF python library in the Pypi webpage (<https://pypi.org/project/ndvi2gif/>). The front picture is a timeframe of NDVI maximum values of an intensive agricultural site in the US.

And the available EO datasets are the following:

- **Landsat**
 - [Landsat 4 TM](#)
 - [Landsat 5 TM](#)
 - [Landsat 7 ETM+](#)
 - [Landsat 8 OLI](#)
 - [Landsat 9 OLI](#)
- **Sentinel**
 - [Sentinel 1](#)
 - [Sentinel 2](#)
- **MODIS**
 - [MOD09A1](#)

All NDVI2GIF features are summarized in table 2. By default, NDVI2GIF uses maximum NDVI as a seasonal reducer to avoid clouds and cloud shadows. Any combination of different statistics and datasets can be used. Landsat and MODIS datasets are used in Surface Reflectance (SR) values, while Sentinel 2 dataset uses Top-Of-Atmosphere (TOA) reflectance data. This is because surface reflectance for Sentinel 2 has only been available since 2017, but TOA is available since 2015. Backscattering values of Sentinel 1 bands, HH polarization, can also be used to combine with vegetation indices. This may

eventually be useful for crops, where a higher value of retro is related to a higher plant height (Yang et al. 2022).

The operation of NDVI2GIF is based on Google Earth Engine reducers (Figure 6), which allows to obtain pixel-level statistics for a selected time series of images. For T4.4. purposes, NDVI2GIF uses three time intervals to group the scenes and produce the RGB composites:

- Seasonal: Seasons of the year (4).
- Monthly: Months of the year (12).
- Bi-weekly: Every 2 weeks (24).

Table 2: Available datasets and statistics provided by NDVI2GIF.

Dataset	Spatial Resolution	Temporal Resolution	Indices	Temporary Availability	Stats
Landsat (Landsat Surface Reflectance collections merged from Landsat 4-TM to Landsat 9-OLI)	30 m	7 days	NDVI EVI SAVI GNDVI AVI	1984-Present	Maximum Minimum Mean Median Perc 90 Perc 95
Sentinel 2	10 m	5 days	NBRI NDSI AEWI AEWINSH	2015-Present	
Sentinel 1	14 m	6 days		2014-Present	
MODIS MOD09A1	500 m	Daily		2001-Present	

With NDVI2GIF, it is possible to produce seasonal composites with pixel values of the selected statistic for all available images covering the selected period. It is a very useful tool to calculate the phenology metrics with *PhenoPy*. As NDVI2GIF integrates *deimspy*, composites can easily be retrieved for any eLTER site.

Figure 6: Example of reduction of GEE time series of vegetation index images.

The use of NDVI2GIF is very similar to the use of PyVPP. The user has to select the dataset, the vegetation index, the time interval and the statistic to reduce the time series of images. DEIMS ID has

also to be entered to choose the user eLTER site. Moreover, the user can also upload any shapefile of polygons defining the boundaries to be applied. The following commented code block provides an example of how to use NDVI2GIF:

```
#Import the main class NdviSeasonality. Noticed that there's also a
#get_stats method which can be used to get zonal statistics
from ndvi2gif import NdviSeasonality, get_stats
#Define Sentinel 2 max values of NDVI one per each month of the year
#In that deimsID (Donana LTSER) for the period 2020-20222
#This will create 3 rasters collections with 12 bands
#One per month per year
ltserDonana = NdviSeasonality(roi='deimsid:https://deims.org/bcbc866c-
3f4f-47a8-bbbc-0a93df6de7b2', sat='S2', key='median',
periods=12,start_year=2020,
                                end_year=2022, index='ndvi')
#Do the magic
s2 = ltserDonana.get_year_composite()
```

Figure 7 shows the output of the previous code block. The RGB composite evidences the land use cover dynamics. Bright colored pixels indicate high NDVI values throughout the year while dark colors are shown by pixels with low greenness values throughout the selected time interval. Shaded colored areas denote land use and land covers reaching maximum NDVI at different moments of the year.

Figure 7: Example of a seasonal composite (image and time profile from the pixel identified by the cross) of Sentinel 2 maximum NDVI images for a monthly period at Doñana LTSER Platform.

A video tutorial (Figure 8) with full description on the use of NDVI2GIF has also been created (<https://youtu.be/kJkX6aVXBws>).

Figure 8: Screen capture of the NDVI2GIF video tutorial.

The Jupyter Notebook used in the video tutorial is located on the [GitHub repository of the package](#), and is also available in DataLabs (ndvi2gif.ipynb in the 'Notebooks' section under GeeLTERMap repository in the eLTER RI project). All notebooks stored on GitHub can be launched in Google Colab just by typing "tocolab" in the url. For instance, the following link will open the ndvi2gif jupyter notebook used in the video tutorial in the Google Colab virtual environment:

<https://githubtocolab.com/Digdgeo/NDVI2GIF/blob/master/ndvi2gif/ndvi2gif%20extended%20version.ipynb>

2.3 GeeLTERMap: Integrated tool for phenometrics, inundation and LST mapping

The [GeeLTERMap](#) python package has been created as a resource for scientists and site managers from the eLTER network to retrieve the selected task 4.4. SO.

GeeLTERMap is based on the [Geemap python package](#), a Python API that allows easy access to Google Earth Engine (GEE) datasets and algorithms and provides an interactive map interface (Gorelick et al. 2017). Additionally, through GeeLTERMap, the user has access to all alphanumeric and spatial information from the eLTER Sites as *deimspy* is integrated into the tool. Furthermore, by enabling access to all relevant site-related information, the user can set customized filters for eLTER Sites to apply GeeLTERMap specific procedures.

GeeLTERMap includes three different tools (PhenoApp, FloodApp and LSTApp), each one identified by three different color buttons integrated into a Geemap map environment (Wu 2020). Each button provides access to one of these three basic tools of GeeLTERMap described in the following sections (Figure 9). Additionally, a survey form has been included to enable users to submit in-situ data for validation purposes.

A video tutorial illustrating the use of all three tools of GeeLTERMap is available online (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=unxqGwAcBfA&t=2439s>).

Figure 9: Technologies integrated in GeeLTERMap.

2.3.1 PhenoApp: Mapping phenology metrics

PhenoApp was jointly created under eLTER PLUS and SUMHAL-LifeWatch ERIC projects as a tool for eLTER PIs and managers. This application enables the user to retrieve and calculate Land Surface Phenology metrics of the different land covers in their sites. The application features a dynamic map (Figure 10) which allows eLTER Site selection to visualize phenology metrics for individual or grouped pixels. These “phenometrics” are generated using Sentinel 2 time series of images processed with the Python libraries *NDVI2GIF* and *PhenoPY*. Additionally, PhenoApp includes the MODIS phenology product (MCD12Q2.006) and the Copernicus Sentinel 2 High Resolution Vegetation Phenology and Productivity Product (HR-VPP). PhenoApp also provides a survey form button to enable users to upload in-situ data on observed phenology metrics collected either by direct observation or phenocams (see section 6.1.), which will be used to provide a validation assessment of the different EO products.

Figure 10: PhenoApp mapping interface showing the phenometric Maximum of Season (MoS) of the year 2017 calculated using *Phenopy* package with Sentinel-2 images for Doñana LTSE platform.

PhenoApp uses Google Earth Engine by means of the Geemap library, enhancing the use of GEE servers and algorithms by including Python programming and libraries for data processing. PhenoApp incorporates the [Leafmap](#) mapping application. Leafmap integrates dynamic map services within the Python environment, particularly in development environments based on the Jupyter project (Kluyver et al. 2016), including Jupyter Notebooks, Jupyter Labs, or Google Colab. PhenoApp can be used locally or through any of these environments, including Datalabs which hosts a Jupyter environment for eLTER PIs.

Geemap dynamic maps enhances user interaction by managing communication between the backend and frontend of any developed application. Geemap enables the design of web map applications, like GeeLTERMap, and editing of widgets featuring graphical user interfaces and specific functionalities required by developers when executing code. As previously mentioned, GeeLTERMap including PhenoApp tool is available in the Datalabs.

PhenoApp is a pilot application that currently serves visualization and download of three phenology products:

- **Sentinel-2 based phenometrics calculated with *Phenopy*:** *PhenoPY* takes a stack of Sentinel-2 ([L2A dataset of surface reflectance](#)) NDVI images and a text file containing the dates for each image. The software then applies a smoothing algorithm using cubic splines to the curves and calculates the phenological transitions. *PhenoPY* allows two procedures to perform curve smoothing and identification of inflection points (Figure 11): based on a single threshold (*Phenopy_U*) or based on the derivative (*Phenopy_d*). This implementation requires pre-calculation for eLTER Sites to be visualized and downloadable. So far, the following sites have been pre-calculated for validation purposes (see Figure 12): Baixo Sabor (Portugal), Braila Island (Romania), Cairngorms (UK), Doñana (Spain), Gran Paradiso (Italy), Neusiedler (Austria), River Exe (UK), Schorfheide (Germany) and Veluwe (Netherlands).

- **MODIS phenology product:** ready for visualization and download for all eLTER sites
- **Copernicus HR-VPP phenology metrics:** This implementation requires pre-calculation for eLTER Sites to be visualized and downloadable. So far, pre-calculation has been done for the previously identified eLTER Sites for validation purposes. The PyVPP package enables users to download HR-VPP products for any eLTER Site.

Figure 11: Phenology metrics calculated with PhenoApp. Modified from Tian et al. (2017)

Figure 12: Initial dynamic map of PhenoApp mapping interface showing the nine sites for which PhenoPy and HR-VPP products have been pre-calculated.

The current workflow of PhenoApp is illustrated in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Workflow of the PhenoApp tool with all the external sources and packages.

The user selects a eLTER national network and site and the dynamic map shows the boundaries of the site with a default NDVI2GIF RGB composite of mean NDVI as default background. User has to select among the three available phenology products. Available datasets and phenology metrics are summarized in table 3. By selecting MODIS phenology product a layer will be overlaid according to the phenology metric selected and its value (SOS, MOS or EOS, Day of Year -DoY- or vegetation index value). in-situ data collected for every eLTER Site can be provided through the FormApp (section 4.3.3.) in order to validate the different phenology products.

Table 3: Summary of PhenoApp products of phenology metrics.

Dataset	Satellite	Growing Cycles	Start Year	Index	Spatial Resolution	Phenometrics
HR-VPP	Sentinel 2	2	2017	PPI	10 m	SOSD SOSV MOSD MOSV EOSD EOSV
MCD12Q2	MODIS	2	2001	EVI	500 m	
PhenoPy	Sentinel 2	1	2015	NDVI	10 m	

PhenoApp was successfully presented in the XIX Congress of the Spanish Association of Remote Sensing, held in Pamplona, Spain, from June 29th to July 1st, 2022. It was selected to be featured as a case study in the association's journal, where the article "PhenoApp: A Google Earth Engine-Based Tool for Monitoring Phenology" was published on December 16th, 2022 (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4995/raet.2023.18767>). PhenoApp tool was also presented at the in person *eLTER Software workshop* organized by WP5 in Lyon, France on February 7-9th 2023 (Figure 14). This meeting allowed a first contact and feedback from PIs of different sites with available in-situ phenological data for their sites and interested in the validation of PhenoApp Earth Observation products.

Figure 14: Oral presentation of PhenoApp tool at the Lyon "eLTER Tools" workshop.

2.3.2 FloodApp: Mapping water surface (inundation/flooding)

FloodApp (Figure 15) is a tool which allows mapping the water area of eLTER Sites for a selected period or date. The tool uses the full Landsat time series of images from Landsat satellites (L4, L5, L7, L8 and L9), covering the 1984-2021 period, as well as the Sentinel 2 time series starting from 2017. The tool also enables retrieving pixel statistics in the case the user selects a time period covering multiple images. Statistics include minimum, maximum, mean, median, and percentiles of 10th, 20th, 90th, and 95th for different water indices calculated with the spectral bands of Landsat and Sentinel-2 sensors (TM, ETM+, OLI, OLI2 and MSI). FloodApp includes the following water indices (Table 4): NDWI (McFeeters 1996), NDWI (Gao et al. 2015), MNDWI (Xu 2006) and AWEI(SH) (Feyisa et al. 2014). Sentinel-2 band 12 and Landsat band 7 located in the SWIR region are also available in the list together with water indices according to the validation exercise carried out for Doñana marshes (see section 6.2). Users can also set a threshold on any of the indices and bands to assess the area discriminated as flooded or inundated. in-situ data collected for every eLTER aquatic site can be provided through the FormApp (section 4.3.3.) in order to validate the different thresholds and indices.

Table 4. Equations and Sentinel-2 bands used for the calculation of the water indices used by FloodApp.

INDEX	EQUATION	SENTINEL-2 BANDS
NDWI_McFeeters	$(GREEN - NIR)/(GREEN + NIR)$	$(B03 - B08)/(B03 + B08)$
NDWI_Gao	$(NIR-SWIR) / (NIR+SWIR)$	$(B08-B11) - (B08+B11)$
MNDWI	$(GREEN - SWIR)/(GREEN + SWIR)$	$(B03 - B11)/(B03 + B11)$

AWEI(SH)	$BLUE + 2.5 \times GREEN - 1.5 \times (NIR + SWIR) - 0.25 - SWIR$	$[B02 + 2.5 \times B03 - 1.5 \times (B08 + B011) - 0.25 \times B12]$
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Figure 15: FloodApp dynamic map interface showing the surface water in Braila Island LTSER platform based on median AWEI values for the year 2022.

Images used to calculate the water indices can be filtered based on cloud cover in order to exclude highly cloud covered scenes from the calculation. Also, a RGB composition using NDWI and calculated by NDVI2GIF tool is available for the selected period, though its display is disabled by default. Such composites may provide the user a synoptic view of the inundation process along the selected period. The visualized product can be downloaded to local or virtual environments (DataLabs, Google Colab, etc.).

Table 5 shows the specifications of the datasets used by FloodApp and statistics are summarized in the table below. In the video tutorial of GeeLTERMap ([GeeLTERMap](#)), a specific example is provided on the use of PhenoApp.

Table 5: Specifications of datasets and products used and provided by FloodApp.

Dataset	Water Indexes	Start Year	Temporal Resolution	Spatial Resolution
Sentinel 2	NDWI (McFeeters) NDWI (Gao) MNDWI	2017	5 days	10 m
Landsat 4-9 (TM, ETM+, OLI)	AWEI SWIR-2	1984	8 days	30 m

2.3.3 LSTApp: Mapping Land Surface Temperature

The Land Surface Temperature tool (LSTApp, Figure 16) also uses Google Earth Engine API to access LST products from MODIS ([MOD11A1](#)) and Landsat ([TIRS](#)) collections. Specifications of both datasets are shown in Table 6. LSTApp provides users with options to select any eLTER Site, sensor collection, start and end dates, filter by scene percent cloud coverage for Landsat or using the MODIS quality band, and choose the LST product and the statistics for image reduction when indicating a timeframe. Likewise for the PhenoApp and FloodApp, a legend on LST values (°C) can be displayed if desired on the screen. Users can also download the visualized images. Download limitations may rise according to user platform when downloading a complete LST scene at high spatial resolution covering the eLTER Site. However, users can always define an area of interest using the map drawing tools on the left side of the dynamic map. The GeeLTERMap video tutorial also provides an example on the detailed use of LSTApp.

Figure 16: Snapshot of LSTApp dynamic map interface showing median LST values for three months of 2023 from Landsat TIRS Band 10 of Gran Paradiso eLTER site. Bar legend on the left expands for more colors while running the tool.

Table 6: Specifications of datasets and products used and provided by LSTApp.

Dataset	Products	Start Year	Temporal Resolution	Spatial Resolution
MODIS MOD11A1	LST_Day LST_Night Emissivity	2001	5 days	1 km
Landsat 8-9 SR TIRS	ST_B10 Emissivity	2013	8 days	30 m (*100 m native resolution)

2.3.4 FormApp: Upload of in-situ data by user (eLTER PIs)

Task 4.4. seeks to assess the accuracy of the EO products provided by the different agencies using the valuable in-situ datasets provided by eLTER sites network. Validation of satellite-derived products is essential to enhance and enlarge their use by any user. GeeLTERMap provides and generates EO products such as water masks, LST and phenology metrics for any eLTER site through an interactive dynamic map but it is still necessary to include specific assessments on their accuracy according to in-situ measured data provided by eLTER Site PIs. In order to enable the users uploading their in-situ datasets for the specific SO we have implemented FormApp. Under GeeLTERMap the user can invoke FormApp (Figure 17) by pushing its red icon, which makes the menu pop up offering different upload options. Users are invited to write the in-situ data collector's name and email, along with the selected site, the coordinates (latitude and longitude) of the measurement point, the year of the measurement and the SO (Phenometrics, Flood and LST) for which the user provides the in-situ data. If the user is providing phenometrics data, he/she should also select the metric (SOS, MOS or EOS) and the Day of the Year (DOY) of the metric. If the user is providing Water presence (Flood/Inundation) data, he/she should also tick the water presence option and can append the information on the water level by using the specific bar. Finally, if the user is providing LST data, he/she should only provide the in-situ measured surface temperature. All data will be uploaded to a "validation_data.txt" plain text file, which will be further used for validation purposes. FormApp also gives the option to upload a user-defined CSV file with many in-situ measurements which will be stored in the DataLab root folder. An exemplary CSV is provided in Datalabs GeeLTERMap repository as a template for phenometrics in-situ provision (Table 7).

The screenshot displays the FormApp interface overlaid on a satellite map of Europe. The form includes the following elements:

- eLTER Network:** A dropdown menu.
- eLTER Site:** A dropdown menu.
- Collector Name:** A text input field.
- Collector Email:** A text input field.
- Insert Latitude Coord (decimal degrees):** A text input field containing the value 37.8756.
- Insert Longitude Coord (decimal degrees):** A text input field containing the value -6.8756.
- Upload file:** A button with a file icon and the text "Upload file".
- Upload (0):** A button with an upload icon and the text "Upload (0)".
- Year:** A horizontal slider set to 2017.
- Show Ndvi2Gif NDWI composite:** A checked checkbox.
- PhenoMetrics, Flood, LST:** A set of tabs with "PhenoMetrics" currently selected.
- Phenometric:** A dropdown menu.
- DOY:** A horizontal slider set to 162.
- Apply, Reset:** Two blue buttons at the bottom of the form.

Figure 17: View of FormApp main menu to upload in-situ data for validation of the SO.

Table 7. Example of CSV file to provide in-situ data on phenometrics through FormApp for validation purposes.

Land cover	Date	Phenometrics	Lat	Lon
<i>Pinus pinea</i>	20220315	SOS	-6.1245	38.3422
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	20220517	SOS	-6.1	39.2578
<i>Pinus nigra</i>	20220228	SOS	-5.58	37.4023

3 Implementation in DataLabs and usage

Our three tools are located in the DataLabs portal, in the 'Notebooks' section under GeeLTERMap repository in the eLTER RI project (Figure 18), and can be accessed through the following link for registered users: <https://datalab.datalabs.ceh.ac.uk/resource/elter/pyvpp/tree/>. Datalabs requires users to [sign up](#).

Figure 18: Location and view of the GeeLTERMap repository in DataLabs and the Jupyter Notebooks included once the user clicks the Open tab.

Once opened, Geeltermap environment in Datalabs shows one jupyter notebook for GeeLTERMap (GeeLTERMap.ipynb), one for NDVI2GIF (ndvi2gif.ipynb) and one for PyVPP (pyvpp.ipynb) tools. Users can also find in the repository: a CSV file (CSV_file_example_for_phenometrics.csv) that can be used as template for in-situ data upload, four NDVI images of Doñana eLTER Platform that are used by NDVI2GIF, and two text files, one containing the links to video tutorials for the three developed tools (video_tutorials_links.txt) and another text file as an example of the file generated by FormApp with the user-provided information for validation (example_validation_data_file_uploaded.txt). By double-clicking one of the jupyter notebooks it will open up in a new window where a classical Jupyter Notebook interface will appear (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Main view of GeelTERMap Jupyter Notebook opened in Datalabs.

As mentioned before, any of the notebooks can be run in other virtual environments such as Google Colab or Jupyterlab for instance. For doing so, the user can download the notebook and upload it to the virtual environment. Users can also run the notebooks in the user's local computer with the only request to have pre-installed the [GeeMap](#) package. For GeelTERMap, users need to have a registered user for Google Earth Engine tool, which will be requested when executing the second cell of the Jupyter notebook, by requesting a token and offering a link to generate the token linked to the user GEE account.

4 Validation of Earth Observation products

Although remote sensing provides a practical way to acquire key parameters efficiently and frequently on a global or regional scale, most of the parameters cannot be directly observed, but are indirectly-calculated from satellite observations through retrieval algorithms. Due to the inherent complexity of the physical processes of electromagnetic propagation and their parameterization, satellite retrievals inevitably suffer from errors, which will finally bias the application of remote sensing (Wu et al. 2019). The theoretical steps for the calibration and validation of satellite missions were described in (Sterckx et al. 2020) (Figure 20). Calibration and validation activities for satellite missions include pre-launch calibration, in orbit calibration, satellite reference calibration. To get calibrated Level-1 data (e.g. radiance, reflectance and transmittance), post-launch calibration and verification is required. The calibrated Level-1 data are a prerequisite for the retrieval of geophysical Level-2 products (geophysical and geochemical parameters). For the generation of long-term series of satellite data (or climate data records), satellite intercomparisons need to be carried out to quantify potential bias between successive sensors. The calibration and validation of satellite missions include the algorithm verification as well as the validation of Level-2 and Higher-Level products. In the product validation, independent estimates of the same measure are compared to the satellite product. In this step eLTER RI could support the validation of a range of geophysical products (and ancillary data for satellite retrievals). Ideally, Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRMs) that are in-situ observations tailored to satellite validation needs, are utilized in the product validation (Figure 21).

Figure 20. Steps for comprehensive calibration and validation activities for satellite missions from Sterckx et al. (2020). Blue boxes show the steps for the production of geophysical satellite data products and green boxes indicate specific calibration and validation activities.

Figure 21. Requirements for in-situ observations in order to be fit for satellite calibration and validation from Sterckx et al. 2020.

Deliverable 3.2 defines the requirements of in-situ observations to be used for cal/val purposes. Requirements for the in-situ observations include sufficient spatial and temporal coverage and information on their spatial and temporal representativeness (site characteristics and sampling design). Access to in-situ data needs to be timely, open and sustainable. Ideally, FRMs uncertainty and uncertainty due to imperfect spatial and temporal co-location need to be well characterized. The

arrangement of multiple reference data at a site (e. g. supersites with geophysical, geochemical and atmospheric data sets) would be highly beneficial for the validation of multiple products and sensors.

There is limited awareness of the required coverage (in parameter space as well as spatially and temporally) and the requirements for FRM quality and documentation of the measurements in order to be useful for satellite Cal/Val. Task 4.4. pilot validation exercise can document the different EO products by including in the metadata file the accuracy estimated from sites-specific validation results. Downstream services provided in the future eLTER RI should provide the products for any eLTER site including a validation accuracy assessment in the metadata for sites providing in-situ data. Available in-situ datasets from eLTER Sites through eLTER repositories will be also used for validation. However, for the selected SO we could not find suitable datasets in DEIMS-SDR, so our general recommendation is to use the FormApp to upload in-situ datasets for the selected SO.

4.1 Validation of Land Surface Phenology metrics

Land surface phenology (LSP) may be defined as the seasonal pattern of variation in vegetated and non-vegetated land surfaces observed from remote sensing. LSP dynamics mostly reflect the response of vegetated surfaces of the earth to seasonal and annual changes in the climate and hydrologic cycle. Vegetation phenology is the timing of repeated biological events, e. g., leaf emergence, flowering, leaf coloration, and leaf fall. Vegetation phenology obtained from time series of remote sensing data is relevant to fully understand climate change effects.

The freely available Sentinel-2 imagery at a 10 m spatial resolution with a ~5-day repeat cycle provides an opportunity to map vegetation phenology at an unprecedented fine spatial scale (Tian et al. 2021). Under the framework of Task 4.4 we have developed PhenoApp which includes the modeling of phenological metrics using Sentinel-2 time series of NDVI or EVI images and metrics provided by the MODIS MCD12Q2 product. Once developed, the Copernicus Land Team released the High Resolution Vegetation Phenology and Productivity (HR VPP) product (available through WEKEO data portal) which uses a similar approach from Sentinel-2 PPI (Plant Phenology Index) images, so we included these datasets in the validation exercise.

There are several available datasets useful for phenology validation. Direct ground observations are very common, such as the ones provided by the Pan European Phenology (PEP725) project. In general, in-situ phenology was considered representative of local vegetation, in particular dominant trees, and when long-term (>30 years) records were available, correlation with climatic parameters was possible. However, observations are generally made on a limited number of species (usually trees) covering a restricted geographical extent, usually close to population centers, typically confined to two seasons (spring and autumn) and recorded below the canopy (Donnelly et al. 2022).

On the other hand, digital camera networks for phenology such as [PhenoCam](#) have developed and spread out, generating near continuous data for hundreds of sites that are useful for satellite validation purposes (Richardson et al. 2013, 2018). The Red-Green-Blue (RGB) imagery from these cameras is normally used for generating time-series of greenness indices, e.g. the green chromatic coordinate (GCC). The GCC data is calculated from the RGB camera images using the ratio of the green channel digital numbers to the total brightness (summatory of Red, Green and Blue digital numbers of every pixel) of the image as described in Hufkens et al. (2018). The original half-hour GCC time series are aggregated to 1 and 3 days by calculating the 90th percentiles to reduce adverse illumination

effects caused by atmospheric influences such as rain, snow, and fog. Images can be processed for the specific region of interest inside the picture (ROI, i.e., the parts in the image with studied vegetation canopies; there can be multiple ROIs in one image for heterogeneous regions). For the validation pilot exercise we decided to use phenocam derived metrics. The Doñana LTSER platform has eight phenocams, the oldest since 2016, located in different and representative habitats: seasonal marshes, grasslands, perennial woodlands, shrubland, heathland and deciduous woodlands (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Doñana LTSER Platform in Europe and location of the eight phenocams used for the validation exercise. Exemplary land cover pictures of each phenocam are also shown.

There are many different procedures for validation of satellite derived products. LSP belongs to the higher level products family where not only spatial but also temporal validation has to be assessed. In this pilot exercise we compared the metrics, Start of Season (SoS), Peak of Season (PoS), End of Season (EOS) and Length of Season (LOS) from the four different sources: MODIS, PhenoApp, HR VPP and Phenocams.

Given the high resolution of Sentinel-2 data, we did not use the camera location but visually georeferenced the location of each ROI projected to the ground. Depending on the phenocam height we used one to a maximum of ten Sentinel-2 pixels covering the ROI location for the comparison analysis (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Defined ROI for the calculation of Phenology metrics in the projected satellite image (left) of the Doñana Torre Palacio phenocam (yellow dot) over the Sentinel-2 pixel grid (blue lines) and over the phenocam picture (shadowed polygon in the right picture).

Nevertheless, as phenocam images usually have a lateral or oblique point of view and satellite images are captured from a zenithal perspective, specific geometric corrections should be applied case by case. Under the framework of T4.4 we set up in the field Ground Control Points (GCP) to estimate the horizontally projected visible ROI to retrieve the corresponding area in Sentinel-2 images (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Visible location of GCP located for Juniper phenocam to enable geometric correction of the image field of view in a projected Sentinel-2 nadiral view.

On the other hand, ROI averaging of pixel values observed by the phenocam are also biased by the prominent elements in the forefront. This issue can be reduced by placing ROI areas in such elements or by applying Inverse Distance Weighting models in the calculation of GCC for the observed ROI. In addition, radial lens correction is also recommended in the georeference processing.

We first assessed the sensitivity to phenological metrics by every method for three consecutive years (2018-2020). Figure 25 depicts the Day of Year (DOY) of SOS, MOS and EOS for every land cover and method along the three consecutive years. For all comparisons, the Phenopy_d method seems to be the least sensitive in relation to the phenocam in-situ values. Conversely, HR VPP captures pretty much the dynamics of all land cover types.

Figure 25. Day Of Year (DOY) of SOS, MOS and EOS phenology metrics for every land cover and method along 3 consecutive years (2018-2020).

Among the different metrics, MOS seems to be the most accurately estimated by the different phenological products for all land covers used in the validation pilot exercise (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Box-whisker plots of the 4 different phenology metrics (DOY values) for the four different EO products (MODIS, HR-VPP, PhenoPy_U and PhenoPy_D) versus the phenocam values for all land covers in the validation exercise using Doñana phenocams.

We used in-situ phenocam derived metrics to estimate Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) for the different EO products (Figure 27) for all available years (2017-2021). Overall, the most accurate EO product was the HR-VPP with an average RMSE of 56 days for all metrics and land covers. PhenoPy_U, the specifically developed method for Task 4.4. based on thresholding the transitions, shows an average RMSE of 60 days, followed by MODIS product with 64 days and PhenoPy_D with a very high RMSE value of 119 days. In assessing the RMSE metric by metric, SOS, EOS and LOS DOYs estimated by PhenoPy_U were closer to phenocam derived metrics. Only for MOS the HR-VPP product provided less RMSE values of 34 days in comparison to PhenoPy_U RMSE of 82 days on average. It seems that both methods would be the most accurate to monitor long-term changes in phenology for different land covers.

However, as the eight phenocams used for this pilot validation exercise are pointing at very different land covers, including inundated areas, the assessment of RMSE also reveals the most accurate EO products per land cover (Figure 28). Table 8 shows the average RMSE values for all metrics estimated by the different EO products according to the monitored land cover. PhenoPy_U methods show the most accurate estimates unless for Heathland (dominated by *Erica* sp.) and Juniper woodlands, for which the HR-VPP products show a closer estimate of all metrics.

Figure 27. Average RMSE in days, calculated for the different EO products available for every phenology metric (SOS- Start of Season, MOS- Maximum of Season, EOS- End of Season and LOS- Length of Season).

Figure 28. Average RMSE in days calculated for the different EO products available for every phenology metric (SOS- Start of Season, MOS- Maximum of Season, EOS- End of Season and LOS- Length of Season) and land cover.

Table 8. Average metric RMSE values in days of the different EO products per land cover. Values in red indicate the most accurate product for the specific land cover.

Land cover	MODIS	HR-VPP	PhenoPY_D	PhenoPY_U
Marsh pond	44.91	33.11	71.83	21.46
Shrubland	Not available	39.43	112.25	23.18
Poplar trees	99.60	69.64	126.46	59.20
Water course	54.93	81.55	48.80	48.58
Open marshes	39.41	57.87	68.73	24.27
Heathland	Not available	46.21	157.77	95.35
Juniper woodlands	Not available	30.10	156.05	76.14

4.2 Validation of flooding levels

Sentinel-2 multispectral images are widely used to delineate water bodies, extent and variability (Lefebvre et al. 2019, Bhangale et al. 2020, Pena-Regueiro et al. 2020, Jiang et al. 2021). As water bodies strongly absorb light in the visible to infrared (VNIR) electromagnetic spectrum, Sentinel multispectral bands are suitable to highlight water bodies. Among the different methodologies, the NDWI (Normalized Difference Water Index, McFeeters 1996) is easily calculated using the green (B3) and NIR (B8) bands, and applied to a variety of wetlands (Du et al. 2016) using as threshold values from 0.2 to 1 as surface water (McFeeters 1996). However, reflectance in the visible and NIR regions depends on the reflectance of the submerged soil, the water depth, the amount of suspended particles, and their optical properties (Díaz-Delgado et al. 2006, 2010). The abundance of optically active components, such as aquatic vegetation, phytoplankton, suspended minerals, and dissolved organic carbon directly affect water turbidity and color (Bilge et al. 2003). More turbid water bodies have higher reflectance values in the green and red visible bands (Bustamante et al. 2009). As a consequence, there is not a single combination of bands providing accurate water delineation for all kinds of wetlands (ranging from deep lakes to shallow lagoons with high to low chlorophyll concentrations or suspended solids and covered by macrophytes). Therefore site specific approaches are recommended to select the most accurate method based on ground-truth data.

One pragmatic approach to assess the accuracy of different bands and indices are classification or decision trees (Friedl and Brodley 1997, Rogan et al. 2003). We built classification trees with all ten Sentinel-2 bands and a set of eight multispectral indices (Table 9) for a surface reflectance Sentinel-2 image (Sen2Cor) acquired on 24th April 2017 over Doñana eLTER Platform (Figure 29). For that date we carried out an extensive ground-truth campaign over the inundated marshes covering a transect

of 24 km long with a total number of 933 sampling points representative of an area of 30 m radius. Originally, we assigned five different in-situ classes: In (Inundated), Ss (dry soil), Sh (wet soil), Emp (Damp soil) and En (Waterlogged), while for the analysis they were grouped under Inundated (In, Emp and En classes) or Non-inundated (Ss, Sh). Complete details of in-situ sampling are available at Díaz-Delgado et al. (2016).

By using a random training sample of 80% of the ground-truth points we calculated the best threshold to discriminate between the two grouping classes: inundated versus non-inundated pixels. Predictive accuracy was assessed using the remaining test set from 20% of all sampling points (186 samples) and by computing Cohen's Kappa statistic in order to measure the degree of classification agreement.

Table 9. Different multispectral indices used to assess the classification of water bodies with Sentinel-2 images.

INDEX	EQUATION	SENTINEL-2 BANDS
NDWI	$[(\text{GREEN} - \text{NIR})/(\text{GREEN} + \text{NIR})]$	$[(\text{B03} - \text{B08})/(\text{B03} + \text{B08})]$
MNDWI	$[(\text{GREEN} - \text{SWIR})/(\text{GREEN} + \text{SWIR})]$	$[(\text{B03} - \text{B11})/(\text{B03} + \text{B11})]$
CEDEX	$(\text{NIR}/\text{RED}) - (\text{NIR}/\text{SWIR})$	$(\text{B05}/\text{B04}) - (\text{B05}/\text{B11})$
RE-NDWI	$[(\text{GREEN} - \text{NIR})/(\text{GREEN} + \text{NIR})]$	$[(\text{B03} - \text{B05})/(\text{B03} + \text{B05})]$
AWEI(SH)	$\text{BLUE} + 2.5 \times \text{GREEN} - 1.5 \times (\text{NIR} + \text{SWIR}) - 0.25 \times \text{SWIR}$	$[\text{B02} + 2.5 \times \text{B03} - 1.5 \times (\text{B08} + \text{B11}) - 0.25 \times \text{B12}]$
AWEI (NSH)	$4 \times (\text{GREEN} - \text{MIR}) - (0.25 \times \text{NIR} + 2.75 \times \text{SWIR})$	$[4 \times (\text{B03} - \text{B11}) - (0.25 \times \text{B08} + 2.75 \times \text{B12})]$
B_BLUE	$(\text{BLUE} - \text{NIR})/(\text{BLUE} + \text{NIR})$	$(\text{B02} - \text{B08})/(\text{B02} + \text{B08})$

Figure 29. Location of the ground-truth points used for the validation of water bodies product from FloodApp in the marshes of Doñana LTSEr platform for the 24th April 2017. In (Inundated), Ss (dry soil), Sh (wet soil), Emp (Damp soil) and En (Waterlogged).

The best band/index to discriminate water bodies from non-inundated areas in Doñana shallow marshes was Sentinel-2 MSI B12 (2190 nm) and the threshold reflectance < 0.0561 with an overall accuracy of 97.32% (Omission error = 0.21% and Commission error = 2.68%) and a Kappa Index of 0.90.

However, in order to select the best threshold for a time series of images, it is recommended to perform an inter-scene cross-validation approach (Davranche et al. 2013). The proposed threshold should be consistent throughout years, sensors, illumination angles, and land cover changes. For instance, a Jackknife procedure allows to calculate the classification agreement for each subsample of images, omitting the *ith* observation to estimate the previously unknown agreement value. This inter-scene cross-validation usually consists of three steps:

1. Computing classification trees, using the whole set of training images except for one of them each time, which was used as a validation image.
2. Computing the classification tree using all the training images.
3. Evaluating threshold accuracies from all training images classification tree over the validation image with the ground-truth data for the corresponding date.

Optimal threshold can then be applied to every eLTER Site by systematically producing water masks with its associated accuracy value for all scenes, as validation measurement. FloodApp enables testing different thresholds for the several water indices and bands for every eLTER site, which can be very useful to eLTER PIs in selecting the most accurate method for delineating water bodies or inundation masks. However, users are encouraged to upload in-situ data in order to numerically test the most accurate method.

Additionally, hydroperiod (the number of days a pixel remains flooded or inundated) can be calculated for specific hydrological cycles to evidence inundation trends for different years (Díaz-Delgado et al. 2010, 2016). In fact, hydroperiod can also be validated using permanent limnimetric scales (Figure 30) or water level probes. The eLTER [Data Visualization Portal](#) includes hydroperiod maps for different aquatic eLTER Sites.

Figure 30. Location of the ground-truth points used for the validation of water bodies product from FloodApp in the marshes of Doñana LTSE platform for the 24th April 2017. In (Inundated), Ss (dry soil), Sh (wet soil), Emp (Damp soil) and En (Waterlogged).

4.3 Validation of Land Surface Temperature

For LST validation purposes, calibrated broadband Infrared Radiometers such as the ones provided by Apogee Instruments© or Campbell Scientific IR120 can easily be deployed on site to systematically collect Surface Temperature. In Doñana eLTSER Platform three Campbell and three Apogee sensors were mounted together with Eddy Covariance Tower stations in 2014. Until March 2018 the Apogee sensor model was SI-111 measuring the radiometric radiance between 8 to 14 μm . From 2018 onwards, sensors were replaced by the new model SI-411 with the same specifications (more details on the measuring principles and technology can be found [here](#) for Apogee and [here](#) for Campbell IR120). These radiometers are periodically calibrated using a LAND P80P calibration source from which the precision of the sensors has been assessed in ± 0.2 K (Sobrino et al. 2015, Sobrino and Skoković 2016, Skoković et al. 2017).

For LST validation we used only the data from Fuenteduque site (Figure 31) located in Doñana marshes providing the longest time series of in-situ Land Surface Temperature data (2011-2023). As shown from FloodApp maps, Doñana marshes have a yearly cycle of inundation from autumn to winter, drying out during the spring season. The topography of the marshes is extremely flat, with a maximum elevation difference of 2.5 m. Continuous radiometric temperatures are measured with a Campbell Scientific IR120 radiometer. in-situ LST were obtained after correction of thermal radiance from ground-based measurements of surface emissivity and from downwelling irradiance. In order to characterize the surface emissivity, measurements with the CIMEL CE 312-2 multiband radiometer were performed in dedicated field campaigns to obtain the emissivity changes along the year. Spectral emissivities were obtained from the application of the temperature and emissivity separation (TES) method to the measured thermal radiances (Jiménez-Muñoz and Sobrino 2006).

Figure 31. Location of the ground-truth point used for the validation of LST product from LSTApp and picture of the installation in the marshes of Doñana LTSER platform.

For the MOD11A1 (previously MYD11) product we used the time series of in-situ data from 2011 to 2020 (Figure 32). Average RMSE for the period was 2.28 $^{\circ}\text{K}$.

Figure 32. Regression of MODIS day LST product values versus in-situ LST measurements in Doñana marshes. Left chart shows values from 2011 to 2015 and the right chart those values from 2016 to 2020. Extracted from Skokovic et al. (2022).

Landsat 7 ETM+ and Landsat 8 TIRS were also used for LST validation with LST in-situ measurements for the period 2014-2017. In this case, permanent infrared sensors located in Juniper woodlands and open marshes were also used. RMSE values for LST derived from Landsat 7 ETM+ varied from 1.1°K to 1.3°K, while for LST derived from Landsat 8 TIRS varied from 1.7°K to 2.4°K (Skoković et al. 2017, 2018).

Finally, although the Sentinel-3 LST product has not been included in the LSTApp, we have carried out a validation test (Figure 33). Sentinel-3 imagery was downloaded for the period July-August 2017. Sentinel-3 data included Brightness Temperatures from the SLSTR instrument (level 1 RBT) and the level 2 LST product. L1/RBT data was used to apply the SW algorithm to brightness temperatures (Jimenez et al. 2018). Pixels located at the test site coordinates were identified to extract the L1/RBT and L2/LST values. Atmospherically corrected Sentinel-2 MSI imagery was also downloaded to estimate surface emissivity only for a single date (2017-07-31). Acquisition dates were selected based on a maximum cloud cover over the scenes to guarantee clear sky conditions at least over the test site. In addition to LST SLSTR level 2 product provided by Copernicus SciHub and Wekeo, we applied the algorithm proposed by Sobrino et al. (1996) for the retrieval of LST (SW).

Figure 33. Regression of Sentinel-3 LST Level 2 product values and LST calculated using the SW algorithm versus in-situ LST measurements in Doñana marshes for the year 2017. Extracted from Jimenez et al. (2017).

5 Available datasets for eLTER Sites

As described in section 4, GeeLTERMap can provide visualization and download of the different SO for the user-selected eLTER Site by direct connection to GEE collections. However, some of the products, such as the Copernicus HR-VPP has to be previously processed due to the large storage needed to save the requested raster files. For visualization purposes, Task 4.4 has selected the following nine representative eLTER Sites: [Baixo Sabor](#), [Braila Island](#), [Cairngorms](#), [Doñana](#), [Gran Paradiso](#), [Neusiedler](#), [River Exe](#), [Schorfheide](#) and [Veluwe](#). Site selection was based on representing different countries of eLTER network, and different ecosystems. As previously indicated, by using PyVPP, users can retrieve HR-VPP products for any eLTER Site or specific area. Figure 34 shows four visualizations of SOS and EOS metrics derived from HR-VPP provided by PhenoApp for four of the selected sites.

Figure 34. Screenshot of the PhenoApp dynamic maps showing SOS and EOS DOYs for different eLTER sites in 2021.

Similarly, Figure 35 shows the resulting dynamic inundation maps provided by FloodApp for 3 different aquatic eLTER Sites applying different water indices and thresholds.

Figure 35. FloodApp maps of surface water detected for different aquatic eLTER Sites using different sensors, indices, statistics and thresholds. From top to bottom: Doñana. Sentinel-2 MNDWI, threshold 0, maximum values for February 2010; Braila Islands. Landsat AWEI, threshold 0, median values for the period 1/01/2020-30/06/2020. Neusiedler. Sentinel 2 NDWI_McFeeters, threshold 0.1, percentile 90 values for 2022.

Finally, Figure 36 shows the resulting dynamic inundation maps provided by LSTApp for three different aquatic eLTER sites applying different water indices and thresholds.

Figure 36. LSTApp maps of Land Surface Temperature retrieved for different eLTER Sites and sensors: a) MODIS LST for the single day 04/07/2023 in Doñana; b) Landsat LST for the same day in Doñana ; c) Landsat mean LST for summer 2020 in Veluwe eLTER Site and d) Landsat percentile 20 LST for winter 2022 in Schorfheide eLTER Site.

6 Downstream services through eLTER Digital Visualization portal (DiV)

Main developments under the eLTER Plus project will be made available as downstream services by eLTER RI. Currently, eLTER Plus has identified eLTER RI stakeholders and proposed a Service Portfolio under 6 Thematic Service Areas. Task 4.4 provides some workflows for harvesting from different information sources (Copernicus HR-VPP, Sentinel-2 SR, MODIS, Landsat, etc.) that can be integrated with eLTER data (for all eLTER sites) to create Information Clusters available via eLTER eLTER Digital Visualization portal (DiV). In addition, these datasets can be documented with validation information based on in-situ data from every eLTER Site. For instance, as mentioned in section 4.1., PyVPP can be executed from script to retrieve all the HR-VPP phenology metrics for every eLTER Site and make them accessible through DiV. By now, the pilot datasets are available in the Datalabs Storage repository (<https://elter-elterdata.datalabs.ceh.ac.uk/minio/data/>). Once all datasets are generated and stored, DiV ingestion and publication should be approached with specific workflows (tiling of TIF images for visualization in the [DiV Portal](#) or provision of WebMap Services). Specific procedures have also to be designed to document and store validation in-situ datasets for the Task 4.4 selected SO.

7 Co-location exercise with LifeWatch-ERIC Spain: SUMHAL project

During the timeframe of Task 4.4 development and implementation, a co-location exercise has been carried out with LifeWatch-ERIC through the research project [SUMHAL](#) funded by MICINN through

European Regional Development Fund [SUMHAL, LIFEWATCH-2019-09-CSIC-4, POPE 2014-2020]. Through its WP6 on the “Development of protocols and indicators for monitoring and assessing the condition of the land at multiple scales”, SUMHAL has explored methods to upscale in-situ data to validate EO products using Doñana eLTER Platform as a validation site. Particularly, tasks 6.2 and 6.3 have contributed to assess the outcomes of both initiatives (eLTER and LifeWatch) in managing and providing long-term datasets using FAIR principles and Virtual Research Environment according to the [European Open Science initiative](#). As a demonstration exercise, GBIF-Spain has set up a demo IPT repository where standardized datasets can be published (<https://ipt-demo.gbif.es/>). Metadata on [HR-VPP datasets for Doñana](#) eLTER Platform has been created.

Under the framework of SUMHAL project, other SO have been tested to be validated with in-situ data. CO₂ and water fluxes have been modeled using Copernicus Sentinel-2 images (Gómez-Giráldez et al. *submitted to Remote Sensing*) and validated with in-situ data collected by four Eddy Covariance Flux Towers located inside Doñana eLTER Platform (Figure 37). Results for the marshland ecosystem reveal the reduction of Gross Primary Production (GPP) due to the dramatic drought affecting Doñana for the last five years. Water and CO₂ fluxes, together with phenology, are critical indicators of ecosystem responses to climate change. Additionally, in-situ soil moisture is automatically measured for a large area with fixed and rover Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensors (CRNS). Mesoscale measurements of soil moisture provided by CRNS are more suitable for upscaling to airborne hyperspectral sensors and satellite derived products. Finally, as the incoming European Space Agency’s (ESA) 8th Earth Explorer satellite mission named FLuorescence EXplorer (FLEX) is expected to be launched in 2026, a cal/val program will be developed and implemented. The ESA-FLEX tandem mission aims to remotely detect the Sun-Induced Fluorescence of vegetation (SIF) with a pixel resolution of 300x300 meters. SIF is the light emitted by chlorophyll pigments. It is an accurate proxy for plant photosynthesis and thus an indicator of plant stress. in-situ fluorescence measurements can be achieved by proximal sensors such as [FLOX](#) and airborne sensors such as [Headwall CFL](#).

This successful co-location exercise is a demonstration of the plausible eLTER RI contribution to cal/val initiatives.

Figure 37. Location of Eddy-Covariance Towers in Doñana LTSER Platform and calculated in-situ GPP for the medium rainfall year 2021 (gray line) and for the dry year 2022. Upper chart shows the validation of fluxes using TSEB model upscaled to Sentinel-2 images.

8 Needs, requirements and cost assessment for validation using in-situ data

According to the pilot study we can provide few recommendations on needs, requirements and a rough cost assessment to setup and maintain in-situ data collection of the selected three SOs to be used for validation purposes. eLTER RI can use the coarse cost assessment which is provided on the basis of the installation of a single unit or field campaign.

8.1 In-situ measurements of Land Surface Phenology metrics

The pilot study has revealed the ease of using Phenocameras to monitor systematically vegetated land cover dynamics. Near-surface remote sensing with digital web cameras has become the most widely used source of validation data for satellite-derived land surface phenology. A protocol for the observation of canopy phenology using digital cameras for the ICOS ecosystem sites is available (https://european-webcam-network.net/data/ICOS_Phenocamera_WG_Protocol_final.pdf), including recommendations for camera installation, orientation, and processing as well as metadata. Instructions for the installation and set-up of cameras are also provided by the Phenocam Network in the US (<https://phenocam.nau.edu/webcam/tools/>). There are many algorithms available for the analysis of digital images to create time series of vegetation color indices and determine phenological dates. An example of an open-source software is the Phenopix R package (Filippa et al. 2016). It provides standardized processing algorithms for extraction of vegetation color indices and the dates of phenological events. Additionally, software routines were developed by the Phenocam network in the US, e. g. for the delineation of the region of interest (xROI, <https://github.com/bnasr/xROI>). More recently, the Finnish Meteorological Institute has developed FMIProt, a system for multiple camera networks for continuous monitoring of ecosystems by processing image time series from phenocams

(Tanis et al. 2018), which includes data acquisition, processing and visualization from multiple camera networks. The users can implement their own developed algorithms to extract information from digital image series for any purpose.

Overall, the price for an RGB webcam playing as a phenocam can be very low (~100€). However, the two most widely used models are: [LUPUSNET HD-LE971](#) and [Stardot NetCam SC](#) (Figure 38), which may also include Infrared band (IR model). Both cameras are provided with a protecting case, the necessary material for installation and advanced configuration for streaming/uploading video and images. Prices for these cameras are between 700 and 1000€. Installation requires permanent power supply of 12V which may be provided by a solar panel and a battery. Although these cameras include their own storage cards they can be configured to be integrated into a communication network (wireless or modem) in order to upload daily images for further analysis, which avoids periodic visits to the site to download the collected data. The Stardot cameras are recommended by the Phenocam Network, which provides full assistance in setting up and configuring the camera/s and full processing of images in the case of cameras connected to the internet, including calculation of RGB indices and model fitting for phenology metrics through the [Phenocam Explorer](#) (Figure 39). In addition, these cameras can be programmed to define the frequency of acquisitions per day, allowing the user to select specific time intervals for analysis. They can also be calibrated with a reference calibration panel.

Figure 38. LUPUSNET HD-LE971 and Stardot NetCam SC used for phenological monitoring.

Figure 39. GCC time series provided by PhenoCam Network of the *Donanafuenteduque* phenocam and phenology metrics extracted by PhenoCam Explorer for the same site.

Phenocams require permanent power supply which may be provided by solar electric power systems or direct line power. For sizing the battery bank, the StarDot camera for instance, draws about 1/3 A at 12.6 V. Current costs for the necessary power systems can go up to 500€. As already commented, phenocams can connect to the internet using wireless connection, or eventually cell phone services through cell phone modems such as the ones provided by [CradlePoint](#). Alternatively, phenocam can store the images locally. This can be done, for example, by networking the camera with a data logger. The data logger pulls images from the camera and stores them on a flash card. The flash card can be swapped out during periodic site visits and, on return to the lab, images manually uploaded via FTP to the camera server. This latter option would increase installation costs up to ca. 1200€. Phenocams only require periodic maintenance on re-aligning the field of view in case of shifts caused by wind or external agents as well as periodical cleaning of the box lenses.

8.2 In-situ measurements of Water Bodies/Inundation

Several technologies and instruments are available for continuous water level measurement of wetlands. These instruments are very valuable for permanent wetlands. However, seasonal wetlands may dry out at the location of the sensor which can result in damaging the probe. In addition, large wetlands would require the deployment of a vast amount of probes to accurately provide in-situ validation data for water surface mapping. For these reasons and seeking to provide in-situ data for inundation mapping of the full wetlands extent, it is recommended to carry out periodical field campaigns. Another option is to have in place limnimetric scales (Figure 30) uniformly distributed across the wetland. This conventional procedure to measure water levels requires visiting every single scale to record water level. One smart alternative is to place in front of the scales a ruggedized camera, such as a camera trap, with a periodic shutter program taking pictures for instance every day (Figure 40). It is recommended to place the camera facing northwards to avoid sun glints. Nowadays, there are wildlife cameras provided with SIM cards, which enable remote download of the collected pictures. However it is still necessary to replace batteries, although battery endurance makes them last up to two months depending on setup conditions. Suitable cameras are provided by [Wingscapes](#) or [Wildlife Monitoring Solutions](#) among many other companies. Prices go from 200€ up to 500€ per unit.

Figure 40. Picture taken by a camera located in front of a limnimetric scale showing water level of the wetland. Camera pictures record the date and time and have enough resolution to distinguish the centimetric scale.

Field campaigns should be designed to be coincident with Sentinel-2 or Landsat 8 and 9 acquisitions over the eLTER Site. Overpass schedules are available for any site in the world ([Sentinel-2](#) and [Landsat](#)). Field campaigns should mainly focus on collecting as many different locations as possible inside the wetland area with the purpose to cover as much as possible the inundated area. The minimum required variable to record is water presence or absence. Water presence is defined as a homogeneous cover of standing water at the location coordinates for at least a surface of one to three pixels (for Sentinel-2 100 to 900 m² and Landsat 900 to 8100 m²). GPS coordinates are to be collected

in the center of the area covered by water. Depending on site accessibility, in-situ data collection can be designed for points along a transect, which increases sampling efficiency. In such a case, it is also recommended to record the GPS track. For heterogeneous inundated areas, transects can be done by driving qualified vehicles, riding horses, or just by walking. It is critical to collect not only coordinates for the inundated areas but also for dry locations in order to have a balanced sample. Inundation categories can be more detailed than simply inundated and non-inundated, collecting mixed situations such as damp, wet or waterlogged. Identifying many flooding categories will also help in later classification. Ancillary measurements of water depth, percent of bare water surface and percent cover of aquatic plants (emergent, floating or submerged) are also recommended to better characterize wetlands heterogeneity and test different flood mapping methods and spectral indices. Eventually, water turbidity and chlorophyll concentration measurements can enhance further analysis for other SO, although these require collection of water samples for later application of laboratory analytical protocols.

As for field campaigns, costs will depend on the final number of sampling points, its distribution and accessibility to the wetland. Nevertheless, basic sampling of water presence/absence accessing aquatic eLTER Sites should not require large expenses and will certainly provide valuable datasets for validation.

8.3 In-situ measurements of Land Surface Temperature

As mentioned in section 6.3, there are several field instruments to measure thermal radiance. Apogee Instruments© or Campbell Scientific IR120 rugged sensors can easily be deployed on site to systematically collect Surface Temperature calculated from thermal radiance. Usually, the spectral range of these sensors is from 8 to 14 μm , with an operating temperature range from $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, a manufacturer accuracy of $\pm 0.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a measurement range of $-60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $110\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Apogee radiometers, for instance, are routinely used as a validation source for satellite and UAV-based studies that involve retrieval of LST (Aragon et al. 2020). Field installation and set up of these sensors will require permanent power supply and in-situ data logger recording. Solar electric power systems can amply maintain IR sensors. A data logger is also necessary to store data. A complete installation would cost about 2000€. IR sensors would eventually require re-calibration or vicarious calibration on site, as well as low maintenance to clean up sensor lenses and review sensor position and FOV.

9 Conclusions

The tools and workflows presented herein should be considered as enabling technologies. Hopefully researchers and stakeholders from across the eLTER network will recognize the breadth of historic EO data currently available, along time lines and over the variety of spectral bands. Looking to the future, the exponentially increasing data acquisitions from new satellites present challenges and opportunities that were unavailable only a decade ago.

Therefore, modern ecological research cannot thrive on predefined, static variables. The dynamic workflow presented in this work, and supported by a toolbox of flexible software applications can be the mainstay of provision of downstream services by eLTER RI. It is the authors hope that, moving toward eLTER RI, this approach consisting of elastic and extensible analyses of EO data will become part of the groundwork for eLTER RI services and products.

One of the key conclusions from our work is the immense potential for ecological monitoring through remote observation by integrating vast stores of image datasets and spatial data, such as those provided by Google Earth Engine (GEE), with DEIMS. Both together made it so much easier to provide tailored products for every eLTER Site. What becomes an incredibly powerful tool that paves the way for advanced long-term ecological monitoring and validation of EO products to improve information clusters.

Finally, Geeltermap is a Python tool that will keep evolving in the near future. Next steps will focus on time series analysis (trends, shifts), improve map interactivity and visualization of phenology on the fly for all eLTER Sites through the temporal analysis of Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 time series of images.

10 Acknowledgements

The work was performed within the project eLTER PLUS (Grant agreement No. 871128) funded under the Horizon 2020 programme. The research challenges and science cases contributed to the definition of the requirements for the data sources and for the selection of sites and variables included in the pilot. Both WP10 and WP11 supported the implementation of the demonstrators and the design of the workflow. The work done was aligned with the requirements defined by the eLTER PPP project especially the ones associated with the data services provision. The authors also want to thank Spanish Ministry of Science for funding the CEOS-Spain project (PID2020-112494RB-I00 IPL-LSTM) led by Prof. José Antonio Sobrino and his team at the University of Valencia. Co-location activities have been performed under the framework of [SUMHAL](#) research project funded by MICINN through European Regional Development Fund [SUMHAL, LIFEWATCH-2019-09-CSIC-4, POPE 2014-2020]. Authors are also grateful to [ICTS-RBD](#) for kindly providing full support for the deployment of sensors and data access.

References

- Aragon, B., K. Johansen, S. Parkes, Y. Malbeteau, S. Al-Mashharawi, T. Al-Amoudi, C. F. Andrade, D. Turner, A. Lucieer, and M. F. McCabe. 2020. A Calibration Procedure for Field and UAV-Based Uncooled Thermal Infrared Instruments. *Sensors* 20:3316.
- Bhangale, U., S. More, T. Shaikh, S. Patil, and N. More. 2020. Analysis of Surface Water Resources Using Sentinel-2 Imagery. *Procedia Computer Science* 171:2645–2654.
- Bilge, F., B. Yazici, T. Dogeroglu, and C. Ayday. 2003. Statistical evaluation of remotely sensed data for water quality monitoring. *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 24:5317–5326.
- Bustamante, J., F. Pacios, R. Díaz-Delgado, and D. Aragonés. 2009. Predictive models of turbidity and water depth in the Doñana marshes using Landsat TM and ETM+ images. *Journal of Environmental Management* 90:2219–2225.
- Davranche, A., B. Poulin, and G. Lefebvre. 2013. Mapping flooding regimes in Camargue wetlands using seasonal multispectral data. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 138:165–171.
- Díaz-Delgado, Aragonés, David, Afán, Isabel, and Bustamante, Javier. 2016. Long-Term Monitoring of the Flooding Regime and Hydroperiod of Doñana Marshes with Landsat Time Series (1974–2014). *Remote Sensing* 8:775.
- Díaz-Delgado, R., D. Aragonés, I. Ameztoy, and J. Bustamante. 2010. Monitoring marsh dynamics through remote sensing. Pages 375–386 in C. Hurford, M. Scheneider, and I. Cowx, editors. *Conservation Monitoring in Freshwater Habitats*. Springer, Dordrecht, Heidelberg, London, New York.

- Díaz-Delgado, R., J. Bustamante, D. Aragonés, and F. Pacios. 2006. Determining water body characteristics of Doñana shallow marshes through remote sensing. Pages 3662–3664 IGARSS 06. IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, Denver, Colorado, USA.
- Donnelly, A., R. Yu, K. Jones, M. Belitz, B. Li, K. Duffy, X. Zhang, J. Wang, B. Seyednasrollah, K. L. Gerst, D. Li, Y. Kaddoura, K. Zhu, J. Morissette, C. Ramey, and K. Smith. 2022. Exploring discrepancies between in-situ phenology and remotely derived phenometrics at NEON sites. *Ecosphere* 13:e3912.
- Du, Y., Y. Zhang, F. Ling, Q. Wang, W. Li, and X. Li. 2016. Water Bodies' Mapping from Sentinel-2 Imagery with Modified Normalized Difference Water Index at 10-m Spatial Resolution Produced by Sharpening the SWIR Band. *Remote Sensing* 8:354.
- Feyisa, G. L., H. Meilby, R. Fensholt, and S. R. Proud. 2014. Automated Water Extraction Index: A new technique for surface water mapping using Landsat imagery. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 140:23–35.
- Filippa, G., E. Cremonese, M. Migliavacca, M. Galvagno, M. Forkel, L. Wingate, E. Tomelleri, U. Morra di Cella, and A. D. Richardson. 2016. Phenopix: A R package for image-based vegetation phenology. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 220:141–150.
- Friedl, M. A., and C. E. Brodley. 1997. Decision tree classification of land cover from remotely sensed data. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 61:399–409.
- Gao, Y., J. Gao, H. Yin, C. Liu, T. Xia, J. Wang, and Q. Huang. 2015. Remote sensing estimation of the total phosphorus concentration in a large lake using band combinations and regional multivariate statistical modeling techniques. *Journal of Environmental Management* 151:33–43.
- Gómez-Giráldez, P., Cristóbal, J., Nieto, H., García-Díaz, D. and Díaz-Delgado, R. Validation of carbon assimilation estimated by remote sensing for Doñana National Park ecosystems reveals water availability as the most accurate factor to retrieve Light Use Efficiency model. Submitted to *Remote Sensing* (25th February 2024).
- Gorelick, N., M. Hancher, M. Dixon, S. Ilyushchenko, D. Thau, and R. Moore. 2017. Google Earth Engine: Planetary-scale geospatial analysis for everyone. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 202:18–27.
- Hufkens, K., D. Basler, T. Milliman, E. K. Melaas, and A. D. Richardson. 2018. An integrated phenology modeling framework in r. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 9:1276–1285.
- Jiang, W., Y. Ni, Z. Pang, X. Li, H. Ju, G. He, J. Lv, K. Yang, J. Fu, and X. Qin. 2021. An Effective Water Body Extraction Method with New Water Index for Sentinel-2 Imagery. *Water* 13:1647.
- Jimenez, J., J. Sobrino, G. Soria, Y. Julien, D. Skokovic, J. Gomis-Cebolla, C. Mattar, A. Santamaría-Artigas, and J. Pasapera-Gonzales. 2017. Early validation results of the land surface temperature product derived from Sentinel-3 SLSTR instrument. *Fifth recent advances in quantitative remote sensing*:206.
- Jiménez-Muñoz, J. C., and J. A. Sobrino. 2006. Emissivity spectra obtained from field and laboratory measurements using the temperature and emissivity separation algorithm. *Applied Optics* 45:7104–7109.
- Kluyver, T., B. Ragan-Kelley, F. Perez, B. Granger, M. Bussonnier, J. Frederic, K. Kelley, J. Hamrick, J. Grout, S. Corlay, P. Ivanov, D. Avila, S. Abdalla, and C. Willing. 2016. Jupyter Notebooks-a publishing format for reproducible computational workflows.
- Lefebvre, G., A. Davranche, L. Willm, J. Campagna, L. Redmond, C. Merle, A. Guelmami, and B.

- Poulin. 2019. Introducing WIW for Detecting the Presence of Water in Wetlands with Landsat and Sentinel Satellites. *Remote Sensing* 11:2210.
- McFeeters, S. K. 1996. The use of the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) in the delineation of open water features. *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 17:1425–1432.
- Pena-Regueiro, J., M.-T. Sebastiá-Frasquet, J. Estornell, and J. A. Aguilar-Maldonado. 2020. Sentinel-2 Application to the Surface Characterization of Small Water Bodies in Wetlands. *Water* 12:1487.
- Richardson, A. D., K. Hufkens, T. Milliman, D. M. Aubrecht, M. Chen, J. M. Gray, M. R. Johnston, T. F. Keenan, S. T. Klosterman, M. Kosmala, E. K. Melaas, M. A. Friedl and S. Frolking. 2018. Tracking vegetation phenology across diverse North American biomes using PhenoCam imagery. *Scientific Data* 5:180028.
- Richardson, A. D., T. F. Keenan, M. Migliavacca, Y. Ryu, O. Sonnentag, and M. Toomey. 2013. Climate change, phenology, and phenological control of vegetation feedbacks to the climate system. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 169:156–173.
- Rogan, J., J. Miller, D. Stow, J. Franklin, L. Levien, and C. Fischer. 2003. Land-cover change monitoring with classification trees using Landsat TM and ancillary data. *Photogrammetric Engineering & Remote Sensing* 69:793–804.
- Skoković, D., J. A. Sobrino, J. C. Jiménez, G. Sòria, Y. Julien, J. Gomis-Cebolla, and S. García-Monteiro. 2018. Vicarious Calibration of Landsat-8 Thermal Data Collections and its Influence on Split-Window Algorithm Validation. Pages 4312–4315 *IGARSS 2018 - 2018 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*.
- Skoković, D., J. A. Sobrino, and J. C. Jiménez-Muñoz. 2017. Vicarious Calibration of the Landsat 7 Thermal Infrared Band and LST Algorithm Validation of the ETM+ Instrument Using Three Global Atmospheric Profiles. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 55:1804–1811.
- Skokovic, D., J. A. Sobrino, D. Salinas, R. Llorens, G. Sòria, J. C. Jiménez, J. Yves, S. García-Monteiro, and B. Franch. 2022. Validación del algoritmo Split Windows de MODIS sobre la estación de Fuente Duque en Doñana. Page 497 *Teledetección para una agricultura sostenible en la era del big data. XIX Congreso de la Asociación Española de Teledetección*. Eds. Luis A. Ruiz, Javier Estornell, María González-Audicana y Jesús Álvarez-Mozos. Pamplona, Spain.
- Sobrino, J. A., and D. Skoković. 2016. Permanent Stations for Calibration/Validation of Thermal Sensors over Spain. *Data* 1:10.
- Sobrino, J. A., D. Skoković, and J. C. Jiménez-Muñoz. 2015. Spatial analysis of the homogeneity of the land surface temperature in three Spanish test sites. *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 36:4793–4807.
- Sterckx, S., I. Brown, A. Kääb, M. Krol, R. Morrow, P. Veefkind, K. F. Boersma, M. De Mazière, N. Fox, and P. Thorne. 2020. Towards a European Cal/Val service for earth observation. *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 41:4496–4511.
- Tanis, C. M., M. Peltoniemi, M. Linkosalmi, M. Aurela, K. Böttcher, T. Manninen, and A. N. Arslan. 2018. A System for Acquisition, Processing and Visualization of Image Time Series from Multiple Camera Networks. *Data* 3:23.
- Tian, F., Z. Cai, H. Jin, K. Hufkens, H. Scheifinger, T. Tagesson, B. Smets, R. Van Hoolst, K. Bonte, E. Ivits, X. Tong, J. Ardö, and L. Eklundh. 2021. Calibrating vegetation phenology from Sentinel-2 using eddy covariance, PhenoCam, and PEP725 networks across Europe. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 260:112456.

- Tian, J., L. Wang, X. Li, H. Gong, C. Shi, R. Zhong, and X. Liu. 2017. Comparison of UAV and WorldView-2 imagery for mapping leaf area index of mangrove forest. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation* 61:22–31.
- Wu, Q. 2020. geemap: A Python package for interactive mapping with Google Earth Engine. *Journal of Open Source Software* 5:2305.
- Wu, X., Q. Xiao, J. Wen, D. You, and A. Hueni. 2019. Advances in quantitative remote sensing product validation: Overview and current status. *Earth-Science Reviews* 196:102875.
- Xu, H. 2006. Modification of normalised difference water index (NDWI) to enhance open water features in remotely sensed imagery. *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 27:3025–3033.
- Yang, H., Li, H., Wang, W., Li, N., Zhao, J., and Pan, B. 2022. Spatio-Temporal Estimation of Rice Height Using Time Series Sentinel-1 Images. *Remote. Sens.*, 14, 546. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14030546>.

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